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EVALUATION OF DISASTER PREPAREDNESS AND AWARENESS TRAINING PROGRAM FOR STUDENT-LEADERS

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ABSTRACT

This research study aimed to conduct and evaluate a Disaster Preparedness and Awareness Training Program for Student-Leaders using a teacher-made survey questionnaire. The study reveals that participants found the training content satisfactory, engaged positively, and experienced post-training behavioral change. The program was also found to be relevant to the needs of the community.

INTRODUCTION

Disaster preparedness and awareness play crucial roles in mitigating the impact of natural calamities hence Republic Act No 10121 recognizes education as a powerful tool for disaster risk reduction and emphasizes including disaster risk reduction (DRR) education within school curricula. It equips students, educators, and youth leaders with the knowledge and skills needed to build a safer and more resilient learning environment. This also ensures that students across all levels acquire essential knowledge and practical skills related to disaster preparedness, response, and resilience.

Student leaders are crucial stakeholders in the school community, empowering learners, influencing peers, and advocating for student benefit. They participate in decision-making processes, including emergency protocols. Investing in disaster risk management (DRRM) training helps them handle crises, coordinate evacuation procedures, and provide support during disasters, fostering a culture of preparedness and resilience.

The information gathered from this study could be used in action planning and could be incorporated into school DRRM plans to promote disaster preparedness and a resilient learning environment.

METHODOLOGY

This study evaluated the researcher-initiated Disaster Preparedness and Awareness Training Program for Student-Leaders using descriptive research designs. The

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three-day training program focused on first aid, basic life support, and disaster preparedness. Invited personnel from the municipal DRRM, FMAG, a non-government agency, and selected members of the school DRRM serve as resource speakers and trainers. was participated by 64 student leaders from various student clubs and organizations. Data was collected through a teacher-made survey questionnaire, validated by experts. Statistical treatment was used to analyze the data. Weighted mean was used to assess disaster preparedness, and One-way Analysis of Variance (One-way ANOVA) was used to determine differences in program evaluation. Participants' comments and suggestions were also collected for improvement.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result shows that participants from all grade levels strongly agree with the training content, with a computed weighted mean of 4.50. Participants were generally engaged during the training, with a verbal interpretation of Agree. The behavioral change criterion ranged from 4.41 to 4.65, indicating successful results in evident behavior change. The criterion of community relevance showed consistent ratings of "Agree" across all grades, indicating that the knowledge and skills attained in the training program is relevant to the needs of the community.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result, it is concluded that the Disaster Preparedness and Awareness Training Program for the Student-Leaders demonstrated success and positive reception across all evaluated criteria and grade levels. The scores consistently show high levels, suggesting positive input or successful results in all criteria across all grade levels.

Keywords: student leaders, disaster preparedness, training program

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